

A bis-azo dye as a chromogenic reagent for determining traces of copper in foodstuffs, blood sera and body tissues

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Abstract : A newly synthesized bis-azo dye, 2,6-bis(1-hydroxy-2-naphthylazo)pyridine has been found to be a very sensitive and highly selective reagent for determining copper. Beer's law is followed upto 1.6 ppm with an optimum concentration range of 0.25–1.0 ppm of Cu^{II}. Sandell's sensitivity was calculated to be 0.0012 µg cm⁻² with molar absorptivity of 5.2 × 10⁴ dm mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 570 nm. Copper has been determined with the reagent in milk, food-grains, tea-leaves, human blood sera and body tissues.

Keywords : Chromogenic reagent, copper determination, spectrophotometry, bis-azo dye, blood sera, body tissues, food stuffs.

Heterocyclic azo dyes¹ (PAN and PAR) have been found to be the excellent chromogens for use in spectrophotometric determination of metal ions. In this laboratory the chromogens such as 2-(4,6-dimethyl-2-pyrimidylazo)-1-naphthol-4-sulfonic acid, 4-(2,6-diamino-4-pyrimidylazo)phenol and 2,6-bis(7-hydroxyacenaphthyl-8-azo)pyridine have been synthesized and utilized². This paper describes the results of synthesis of 2,6-bis(1-hydroxy-2-naphthylazo)pyridine (PBN) and its utility in determining traces of copper in foodstuffs, blood sera and body tissues by spectrophotometry.

Results and discussion

The reagent and its colour reactions :

It is evident from the literature that an azo dye of α-naphthol can be obtained by reacting 1,2-naphthoquinone with an aromatic hydrazine^{3,4}. Thus a bis-azo dye was obtained by reacting 2 moles of 1,2-naphthoquinone with 1 mol of 2,6-dihydrazinopyridine. Its infra-red spectrum confirmed that the compound obtained has an enol-form. The dye showed a light orange colour upto pH 9.0. Below pH 1.5, a hypsochromic shift of 5 nm was observed but a bathochromic shift of 43 nm was seen above pH 9.0. The molar extinction coefficients (ε, dm mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) of the dye at different pH values are 1.8 × 10⁴ (480 nm, pH 0.9), 1.9 × 10⁴ (485 nm, pH 6.0) and 2.7 × 10⁴ (528 nm, pH 11.0) The pK_{NH} and pK_{OH} values are 2.2 ± 0.2 and 19.16 as determined spectrophotometrically.

The ethanolic solution of PBN gave very deep colour with a number of metal ions at different pH values i.e. deep blue to violet colour with zinc(II), cadmium(II), mercury(II), copper(II), silver(I), cobalt(II), nickel(II), manganese(II) in neutral to alkaline media; violet colour with iron(II), vanadium(V) and thallium(I) in alkaline media; green colour with palladium(II) in neutral to alkaline media and a pink colour with chromium(III) in alkaline media. In all these colour reactions the ethanol concentration was kept above 50% to avoid precipitation.

Preliminary studies on colour reactions of PBN with metal ions also showed that in a phosphate buffered medium, only copper(II), iron(II), cobalt(II), nickel(II) and mercury(II) gave coloured complexes. The composition of the complex formed was 1 : 1 as determined by Job's method of continuous variations. The following tentative structure of the complex of bivalent metals with the bis-azo dye may be proposed as :

Further investigations revealed that addition of 2% solution of sodium citrate in phosphate buffered medium

Table 1. Contents of copper in various food-stuffs and biological samples

Sample	No. of analyses	Sample ashed (ml) or (g)	Cu found in whole sample using PBN (μg)	Cu found in whole sample using AAS (μg)	Range of Cu levels (mg/100 ml) or (mg/100 g)
(a) Milk samples :					
Cow	4	100	25.5, 20.8, 21.7, 25.3	22.9, 20.7, 22.1, 25.5	0.0208–0.0253
Buffalo	4	100	24.1, 24.9, 30.3, 22.5	24.1, 24.7, 29.7, 22.6	0.0225–0.0303
Goat	4	100	39.5, 43.0, 42.5, 37.5	39.5, 42.9, 42.0, 38.5	0.0375–0.0430
(b) Food samples :					
<i>Phaseolus aureus</i> (Mung)	4	2	8.94, 7.71, 9.56, 8.34	8.75, 8.15, 8.90, 8.15	0.385–0.478
<i>Oryza sativa</i> (Bran-rice)	3	2	9.86, 10.48, 10.17	10.25, 10.30, 10.45	0.493–0.478
<i>Pennisetum typhoideum</i> (Bajara)	4	5	51.4, 53.76, 54.66, 52.25	51.2, 52.9, 54.05, 53.1	1.028–1.093
<i>Zea mays</i> (Maize)	4	4	61.89, 60.28, 62.7, 61.9	62.7, 61.9, 62.3, 62.5	1.507–1.568
<i>Lens culinaris</i> (Masur)	4	4	22.81, 23.12, 22.5, 22.9	23.3, 23.48, 22.35, 22.85	0.570–0.578
<i>Triticum aestivum</i> (Wheat flour)	4	5	17.0, 17.88, 17.58, 17.9	17.2, 17.35, 17.9, 17.9	0.340–0.358
Milk powder	4	5	15.4, 16.03, 15.8, 14.6	15.65, 16.2, 15.3, 15.2	0.292–0.321
(c) Tea samples :					
Lipton	4	2	10.79, 12.03, 11.71, 11.20	10.98, 12.37, 11.82, 11.29	0.54–0.60
Brooke-Bond	4	2	9.55, 10.79, 10.48, 10.12	9.77, 10.65, 10.93, 10.52	0.478–0.540
Taj	3	2	15.55, 15.24, 13.90	15.85, 15.23, 14.57	0.695–0.777
(d) Human blood sera :					
Normal	6	2.051	2.10, 2.42, 1.98, 1.58, 2.20, 2.07	2.02, 2.31, 2.08, 1.58, 2.0, 2.07	0.099–0.121
Diseased (Malignant breast tumor)	6	1.995	3.85, 3.50, 3.75, 3.35, 3.20, 3.83	3.71, 3.65, 3.89, 3.55, 3.41, 3.67	0.160–0.193
Diseased (Benign breast tumor)	5	1.989	2.16, 1.83, 1.93, 2.08, 2.09	2.82, 2.05, 2.01, 2.18, 2.19	0.092–0.108
(e) Body tissues^a :					
Eye-lens (pooled normal)	4	1.65	1.02, 0.86, 0.78, 1.09	1.11, 1.03, 1.27, 1.25	0.052–0.073

Note

Table-1 (contd.)

Eye-lens (pooled mature senile cataract)	4	1.48	2.75, 2.03, 2.18, 2.16	2.59, 2.31, 2.25, 2.30	0.137-0.186
Prostatic tissue	3	4.92	25.78, 26.08, 30.2	26.3, 26.7, 29.5	0.524-0.614
Carcinoma (prostatic tissue)	3	4.35	55.25, 62.20, 53.07	54.1, 60.2, 54.5	1.22-1.43

^aWet weight was taken.

decomposed all the complexes except that of copper(II), thus making the method highly selective for copper.

Spectrophotometric studies on copper(II)-PBN complex :

Ethanol solution of PBN gave a dark blue complex with copper(II) in neutral to alkaline medium (containing not less than 50% ethanol to avoid precipitation). The maximum and stable absorbance was found at pH 7.0 to 8.5 and phosphate buffer (2 ml, pH 7.6) was found to be suitable to determine copper selectively. The maximum colour intensity was found for Cu^{II} : reagent :: 1 : 5 in molar concentration.

Effect of diverse ions : In the procedure under study 1000-fold of chloride, bromide, nitrate, acetate, sulfate, sulfite, citrate, tartarate, phosphate, borate; and 100-fold of Ca^{II}, Sr^{II}, Ba^{II}, Nb^V, Ta^V, Al^{III} and lanthanides did not interfere, while EDTA, thiosemicarbazide and sulfide interfered seriously. The following anions and cations did not cause a deviation more than $\pm 2\%$:

Anions : Nitrite, oxalate (500-fold); iodide, thiocyanate (100-fold); thiosulfate (50-fold) and fluoride (25-fold). Cyanide (200-fold) however did not interfere, but a hypsochromic shift of 20 nm was observed producing a bright red colour.

Cations : Hg^{II}, Mg^{II}, Sb^{III}, Bi^{III}, Th^{IV} (50-fold); Pb^{II}, Au^{III} (25-fold); Mn^{II}, Ag^I, Mo^{VI}, W^{VI} (20-fold); In^{III}, Pt-metals except Pd^{II} (15-fold); Ti^I, Cr^{III}, U^{VI} (10-fold); Cd^{II}, V^V (5-fold); Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II} (3-fold) and Pd^{II} (4-fold masked by thiocyanate).

Experimental

2,6-Dihydrazinopyridine (0.01 mol) was dissolved in minimum amount of acetic acid and 1,2-naphthoquinone (0.02 mol) was dissolved in ethanol. These solutions were mixed and kept for sometime and then neutralized with ammonium hydroxide to get a red precipitate. The pre-

cipitate was washed with 50% ethanol and dried at 60–70°. Its purity was checked by TLC and elemental analysis. The infra-red spectrum of the compound showed the absence of the $\nu_{C=O}$ (1670 cm⁻¹, for 1,2-naphthoquinone) and $\nu_{C=N}$ (1630–1680 cm⁻¹, for hydrazones) and the appearance of a new strong frequency ν_{OH} (phenolic) at 3200–3500 cm⁻¹, confirming thereby the enol-form of the compound rather than the keto-form. A 5×10^{-4} M reagent solution was prepared by dissolving 0.2092 g of the dye in 1 L ethanol.

A stock solution of copper(II) (0.01 M) was prepared by dissolving copper sulfate pentahydrate in double distilled water and standardized by versenate (EDTA) method. Phosphate buffer (pH 7.6) was prepared as usual. Trisodium citrate solution (2%) was prepared in doubly distilled water.

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade. A Beckman 26 spectrophotometer, Beckman $\Phi 60$ pH-meter and ECIL-4129 atomic absorption spectrophotometer were used.

Samples of milk, food-grains, tea leaves, body tissues, eye lenses and blood sera were prepared by using the reported procedure¹⁻³. Milk was procured from the local dairies and biological samples were procured from the Medical College & Hospital, Rohtak.

Procedure :

An aliquot containing 6–25 μ g of copper(II) was taken in a 25 ml standard flask and 2 ml of 5×10^{-4} M PBN solution, 2 ml of phosphate buffer solution (pH 7.6) and 1 ml of 2% trisodium citrate solution were added to it. The total volume was made upto 25 ml keeping 50% (v/v) ethanol. The absorbance was recorded after 2 min at 570 nm against a reagent blank.

Copper(II) in foodstuffs, blood sera and body tissues etc. : The procured samples were analyzed for copper following the procedure under study. The samples were

also analyzed for copper using an atomic absorption spectrophotometer. The results (Table 1) reveal that PBN can successfully be used to determine copper(II) ions in diverse samples.

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